

1 **A protocol to assess ToxRTool use in peer-reviewed literature**

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18 **Disclaimers**

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25
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37 Hoffmann.

38 **Abstract**

39
40 Context: Study reliability impacts toxicology assessments and the confidence associated with
41 them. Klimisch et al. (1997) first formalised reliability evaluation by standardising study
42 reliability. Then, in 2009 ToxRTool was developed to improve the transparency and objectivity of
43 Klimisch et al. 's (1997) reliability assessment under the EU chemical regulation REACH.
44 Objective: Given the observed trend showing higher ToxRTool use since 2020, we intend to
45 further explore how ToxRTool is used and in what context(s). This protocol outlines our plan to

46 to discuss current usage patterns by summarising ToxRTool applications in peer-reviewed
47 scientific literature.

48 Planned Methods: The JARS-Qual (Levitt et al. 2018) checklist guides this protocol. Since this
49 project assesses toxicological studies, we use study characteristics of interest (e.g., data type,
50 exposure, field of study) and bibliographic information. The search and confirmation of a picklist,
51 code book, and categorization groups has been completed. The search occurred in November
52 2023 where five databases (PubMed, Embase, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar)
53 were assessed without any language restrictions for publications from 2009-2024. After
54 duplication removal, a total of 530 publications were identified and uploaded to Covidence
55 (2025). Of the 530 publications, a randomly selected sample set were used to confirm the
56 eligibility criteria, extraction steps, and decision-making process. The remaining publications
57 have not been assessed nor has any data been extracted.

58 Discussion: ToxRTool helps reviewers evaluate study reliability, so an understanding of how
59 ToxRTool is used or has been modified can inform toxicologists and evidence-based
60 practitioners about current usage patterns. The results could also clarify any incorrect
61 interpretations of ToxRTool use and illustrate useful applications of ToxRTool.

62

63 **Key words**

64 ToxRTool, reliability, assessment, Klimisch, meta-epidemiological

65

66 **1. Introduction**

67 Toxicological studies generate data which then serves as the evidence in chemical hazard and
68 chemical risk assessment. Highly reliable toxicological studies are important because these
69 studies are foundational in assessments. Consequently, reliability assessment of individual
70 studies is an integral part of chemical assessment workflows.

71 Klimisch et al (1997) define 'reliability' as '...the inherent reliability of a test report or publication
72 relating to preferably standardised methodology and the way the experimental procedure,
73 statistical data analysis and results are described to give evidence of the clarity and plausibility
74 of the findings'. They introduced a scoring scheme using the Klimisch Criteria to assess study
75 reliability. The scoring system consists of four categories: 1) Reliable without restrictions, 2)
76 Reliable with restrictions, 3) Not reliable, and 4) Not assignable. Under category 1, reliable
77 without restrictions, a study aligns with valid good laboratory practices (GLP) guidance and the
78 parameters are well documented or at least described to a comparable guideline. For Category
79 2, reliable with restrictions, a study mostly follows GLP guidance and while the parameters do
80 not fully comply with the guidance, the descriptors are sufficient and scientifically acceptable. A
81 study categorized as a 3, not reliable, is one that does not follow an acceptable guidance, there
82 are interfering variables not accounted for, or there are irrelevant exposures tested. For
83 Category 4, a study does not present sufficient parameter documentation.

84 The Toxicological data Reliability Assessment Tool (ToxRTool), was created in 2009 to
85 operationalize the assignment of the Klimisch Criteria. Both *in vitro* and *in vivo* study designs
86 are evaluated under ToxRTool. A series of questions listed in Supplementary Figure 1 address
87 the reporting of relevant parameters for either *in vitro* study design (18 questions) or *in vivo*
88 study design (21 questions). All questions under ToxRTool are evaluated using a binary scoring
89 system assigning 1 or 2 if reported/met or 0 if not reported/met. While most questions are
90 weighted equally, some questions related to plausibility of Study Design and Data are scored as

91 2 if reported/met. Essential questions, such a clear identification of the substance identity, are
92 considered 'Red Criteria' (red in Supplementary Table 1). If any of these criteria are not met, the
93 study reports are assigned to Klimisch Category 3. Once all the questions have a score, they
94 are totalled so the final score determines the study categorization as a Klimisch category 1, 2, 3,
95 or 4. An assessor is also given the opportunity to deviate from the score-based assigned
96 category by providing justification.

97 Aside from Klimisch et al.'s (1997) 'reliability' definition, study reliability is also linked to
98 internationally accepted test guidance, such as the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and
99 Development (OECD) guidelines for testing of chemicals, by categorising such studies as being
100 of high reliability. The European Union (EU) chemical regulation REACH (Registration,
101 Evaluation and Authorisation of Chemicals) stresses this connection by stating 'reliability of data
102 is closely linked to the reliability of the test method used to generate the data' (ECHA, 2007). As
103 the concept of test method reliability evolved over time, the OECD defined 'reliability' as 'the
104 extent that a test method can be performed reproducibly within and between laboratories over
105 time, when performed using the same protocol. It is assessed by calculating intra- and inter-
106 laboratory reproducibility and intra-laboratory repeatability' (OECD 2005, van der Zalm et al.
107 2022).

108 Today, users can select from a variety of tools to assess study reliability. For example, there is
109 the Science in Risk Assessment and Policy (SciRAP) for in vivo, in vitro, in vitro nano materials,
110 and ecotoxicology study designs (Molander et al. (2014). This tool then expanded to address in
111 vitro studies (Roth et al. 2021) and in vitro nanomaterial (Shao et al. 2023). A comparison study
112 by Waspe et al. (2021) assessed ToxRTool, the National Toxicology Program's (NTP) Office of
113 Health Assessment and Translation (OHAT) Risk of Bias (RoB) tool (NTP, 2015) and the Health
114 Assessment Workspace Collaborative (HAWC) when applied to in vivo datasets (Shapiro et al.
115 2018). The authors show how each tool assesses different domains of an in vivo study design
116 along with the approach used to evaluate the domain (e.g., internal validity, study quality, study
117 reliability, RoB).

118 Given the observed trend showing higher ToxRTool use since 2020, we intend to further explore
119 how ToxRTool is used and in what context(s). This protocol outlines our plan to to discuss
120 current usage patterns by summarising common ToxRTool applications in peer-reviewed
121 scientific literature.

122 **1.1 Objective**

123 Citations of ToxRTool, which was published in 2009, have increased substantially since 2020,
124 which prompted the team to investigate this trend and assess how ToxRTool is being used. We
125 aim to discuss current usage patterns by summarising common ToxRTool applications so that a
126 set of recommendations can clarify any misapplications of ToxRTool and guide future uses. This
127 information will be useful for toxicologists, practitioners evaluating toxicological data, chemical
128 risk assessors, toxicological methodologists, reviewers, and editors who will use or may come
129 across publications that apply or compare ToxRTool.

130 The main project goal is to answer the question "How is ToxRTool applied and used in the peer-
131 reviewed scientific literature?" To support this goal several secondary questions are listed below
132 to provide additional context on ToxRTool application and usage:
133

- 134 1. What is the frequency of ToxRTool publication over time?
- 135 2. What are the study characteristics (Figure 4) (e.g., country of first author, year of
- 136 publication, DOI, Intended Use, Field of study, Exposure, Data type, ToxRTool Use)?
- 137 3. What modifications are made to ToxRTool?
- 138 4. What purpose is ToxRTool being used for?

139

140 Based on our results, we aim to develop recommendations as well as ToxRTool do's and don'ts
141 to assist researchers interested in evidence-based methods and assessment of toxicological
142 studies.

143

144 **1.2 Project governance/project team**

145 This is an Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC) driven project approved by the
146 EBTC interim scientific advisory committee (<https://www.ebtox.org>). All team members are
147 contributing as volunteers except for the co-lead (SH), who is supporting the EBTC as a
148 consultant. The project teams' expertise comprises toxicology, evidence-based review
149 experience, systematic review experience, familiarity with ToxRTool, and an information
150 specialist. SH supervised the original ToxRTool development, while the other team members
151 either have used or at least understand how to use ToxRTool. Those with limited to no
152 ToxRTool experience draw upon their toxicological experience. Each team member's
153 toxicological background helps identify relevant information for data extraction. Additional view
154 points are provided through provisional review by the EBTC interim advisory committee as well
155 as lessons learned from each team member's evidence-based methods experiences. Those
156 with prior ToxRTool knowledge helped structure the eligibility criteria and data code book.
157 These team members used the seed publications (Supplementary Figure 2) to illustrate data
158 extraction and facilitate example decision-making processes.

159

160 **2. Methods and Research Design**

161 The JARS-Qual guideline detailed by Levitt et al. (2018) guides the protocol organization
162 (Supplementary Figure 3). This protocol looks at individual studies for key characteristics to
163 categorize ToxRTool applications and modifications. As there are no toxicological specific
164 guidance or checklists for reporting on this type of study design, the JARS-Qual had elements
165 useful for this meta-epidemiological study.

166

167 **2.1 Work Completed: Search Strategy, Confirmation of the Pick list, Code Book, and** 168 **Categorization**

169

170 **2.1.1 Search Strategy**

171 To determine if any similar protocols or projects related to 'ToxRTool' existed, we searched
172 PubMed, PROSPERO, and pre-registration registries ([OSF Registries](#), [protocols.io](#), [Zenodo](#)) on
173 April 8, 2023. No results existed from the search. We then searched PubMed
174 (pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov), Embase (Embase.com), Scopus (scopus.com), Web of Science
175 Core Collection (clarivate.com), and Google Scholar (scholar.google.com) on November 28,
176 2023 without any language restrictions. Grey literature was not searched as our main
177 assumption is peer-reviewed literature would best inform us about ToxRTool application and

178 use. The search strings use the terms “Toxicological Data Reliability Assessment Tool,”
179 “ToxRTool,” and “ToxR-Tool” (Figure 1). The search will be updated since the last search
180 occurred in 2023.

181
182 For an independent citation-based search in each database except Embase, the following three
183 publications were used because they applied ToxRTool or present ToxRTool modifications:
184 Schneider et al. 2009, Segal et al. 2015, and Koch et al. 2016. Schneider et al. presents the
185 development of ToxRTool while Segal et al. presents an analysis of ToxRTool and Koch et al. 's
186 ToxRTool modifications are commonly cited.

187
188 An independent inclusion criterion (Boolean OR) is primarily used in the search string
189 (Supplemental Table 2). Of the 1,674 studies identified, 530 studies were uploaded to
190 Covidence (2025) after deduplication in EndNote (N= 1,114) (Figure 2).

191
192 Covidence (2025) serves as our data management software while EndNote serves as our
193 reference management software. Endnote centralized publication storage and an initial
194 deduplication occurred in Endnote before the publications were uploaded to Covidence (2025)
195 in batches. The Endnote deduplication is independent from Covidence’s deduplication feature.
196 Therefore, the publications uploaded to Covidence underwent another deduplication, which
197 served as a secondary check of any duplicates present.

198 199 **2.1.2 Confirmation of the Picklist, Code Book, and Categorization**

200 SH and KC randomly selected a seed group of publications (N=28, Supplementary Figure 2)
201 from a manual search of the generic term “ToxRTool.” If the publication listed and discussed
202 ToxRTool then the publication was used for the seed group. These publications served as a
203 reference for the pick list in Figure 3 and helped identify the fields listed in the code book (Figure
204 4).

205
206 Using the seed publications, we categorized “ToxRTool Use” as ‘followed (F)’, ‘modified (M)’,
207 ‘added (A) to ToxRTool’, ‘referenced a prior publication’s modification(s) (R)’, or ‘no changes
208 were made (N)’ in Table 3. If the authors ‘followed ToxRTool’ then the tool was used as
209 published in 2009. This categorization allowed us to create a go-no-go point. If a reviewer found
210 the publication does not make any changes, then they do not proceed to the columns with
211 ‘Changes made to...’. If the reviewer determined the authors ‘modified ToxRTool’ or ‘added to
212 ToxRTool’, then the reviewer would categorize the modifications using the remaining six
213 columns in Figure 3.

214
215 From the seed publications we saw several of them referenced another paper’s modification(s);
216 thus we created the option called ‘referenced and used a prior publication’s modification’. If a
217 reviewer selected this option, then they state in the ‘Notes/Comments’ section the original
218 publication referenced. For example, Kirkland et al. (2022) indicated they utilized Card and
219 Magnuson’s (2010) modified ToxRTool. A reviewer would select ‘referenced and used a prior
220 publication’s modification’ for Kirkland et al. and collect the data for intended use, field of study,
221 exposure, and data type. The reviewer would then stop collecting data for any of the ‘Changes

222 made to...’ columns because this information was already collected when Card and Magnuson
223 data was extracted. Through the created categories we hope to reduce redundancies in the
224 data extraction process.

225

226 **2.2 Eligibility Criteria Table**

227 Only full-text publications are assessed with Figure 5 outlining the eligibility criteria with
228 exclusion descriptions. All full-text are sent to the data extraction phase. To further organize
229 potential publications of interest, the “Tags” feature in Covidence (2025) allows reviewers to
230 label studies with a term or phrase of interest. These “Tags” (Supplemental Figure 4) help the
231 team group publications that contain useful reference information but are either outside of the
232 project’s scope or meet a specific type of exclusion criteria.

233

234 **2.3 Data Identification, Collection, and Reporting Process**

235 Any non-English peer-reviewed publications will be translated using Google translate,
236 [DocTranslator](#), or [DeepL](#). If the English translations impair our ability to interpret the published
237 results, then the study will be excluded from full-text screening.

238

239 Data extraction will be based on pick lists for controlled data where appropriate (see Figure 3 for
240 pick list options, see Figure 4 for the code book). Picklist options were tested in piloting. If ‘other’
241 is selected, then a reviewer copies the phrase the authors used into the data extraction form.

242 Any other categories developed will be conducted as a ‘design analysis as we go’ since the
243 open-text responses may yield more details for categorization.

244 As a part of the secondary analyses, bibliographic data such as the first author’s last name,
245 publication year, first author’s country of affiliation, and digital object identifier (DOI) will be
246 extracted. Other bibliographic data will be captured via the Covidence (2025) default features.

247

248 Figure 3 outlines the picklist options for each column’s field of interest. For example, under the
249 column ‘Changes made to “Test Substance Identification”’ a publication could report ToxRTool
250 ‘modified all the question(s)’, ‘met original questions with modifications’, ‘added a question(s)’,
251 ‘added a ‘Criteria Group’, ‘developed a new scoring system’, or ‘none (not mentioned or
252 addressed)’. Aside from the picklists, a reviewer can include their notes, comments, general
253 observations, or any other pertinent details in several open-text sections of the data extraction
254 form. The directions for this open-text state that a reviewer should include the question heading
255 (e.g., “Test Substance Identification”) and the page number the note or comment was referring
256 to. Both SH and KC will review these notes and comments for inclusion in the data analysis or
257 discussion.

258

259 **2.4 Decision-making and Resolution Process**

260 This project uses a two reviewer screening-extraction and resolution process and an
261 asynchronous workflow between six team members. Covidence (2025) will flag any conflicts
262 between reviewers. The conflicting reviewers will coordinate a virtual call to discuss and reach a
263 final resolution, but if no resolution is possible then a third team member will serve as a tie-
264 breaker.

265

266 **2.5 Data Analysis Strategy**

267

268 Figures 6 and 7 illustrate which studies did or did not modify ToxRTool and which
269 modifications were frequently reported. From the data we can identify potential patterns,
270 determine if a particular pattern may be problematic (e.g., risk of bias being a common use of
271 ToxRTool), and assess why modifications were made. The data presented in Figures 6 and 7
272 allow us to assess whether there are common modifications made to ToxRTool or temporal
273 related trends. With the modification data we can assess similarities and differences between
274 publications and also address any potential misconceptions. The combined data will allow us to
275 develop our recommendations for future ToxRTool use, address potential areas of concern, and
276 where follow-up projects could occur since they are out of scope for this protocol.

277

278 As a tool used to evaluate study reliability, the assessment of ToxRTool use and modifications
279 can inform toxicology and evidence-based practitioners. Our recommended dos and don'ts will
280 be invaluable as they can support future directions where ToxRTool is amended or paired with
281 other available tools. Furthermore, our qualitative evaluation of individual studies that use
282 ToxRTool can clarify incorrect applications of ToxRTool use or illustrate useful applications of
283 ToxRTool.

284

285 **2.6 Proposed Data Illustration**

286 Bar charts will illustrate count data for ToxRTool's publication frequency and for study
287 characteristics (Figure 4, Figure 6). Descriptive statistics will describe the frequency of each
288 data category presented in Figure 3 and explore any trends and associations in the dataset.

289

290 To help develop recommendations, the 'Intended Use' category (Figure 3) will be illustrated as
291 a table or figure to show any patterns or common ways authors tried to apply ToxRTool. Then,
292 the 'Intended Use' data can be juxtaposed with the data described in Table 1. This combined
293 data can illustrate different interpretations, applications, modifications, and new additions to
294 ToxRTool.

295

296 **3. Discussion**

297 This protocol describes a single study that will qualitatively assess individual peer-reviewed
298 studies. We aim to assess how ToxRTool is applied and used in the peer-reviewed scientific
299 literature. Our results will be translated into recommendations to inform future ToxRTool users
300 of best practices and the effects of inappropriate applications.

301

302 Our search results may be limited due to a focused search of peer-reviewed publications. This
303 focused search creates a manageable number of studies for the volunteer team to individually
304 assess. This protocol could be updated later to include grey literature. Future research may
305 include expanding this project or assessing other tools in a similar manner. Overall, this project
306 provides useful baseline data regarding ToxRTool use.

307

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